

ICATA 2024

THE FIRST INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE ON ARTIFICIAL
INTELLIGENCE

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence ICATA-2024

IPR in Generative AI: Comparative Law and Contemporary Judicial Interpretations.

MPRamaswamy

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

INTRODUCTION

- The revival and resurgence of artificial intelligence (AI)
- A giant leap of AI technology in the form of generative AI in 2023
- Generative AI is witnessing a conspicuous construction of opensource capabilities

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

INTRODUCTION

- Generative AI has a broader appeal to the masses due to its fundamental ability to transform common people's creative processes and typical tasks.
- Despite the promises, various obstacles remain that need to be addressed effectively to ensure that the full potential of generative AI can be tapped for the benefit of multiple stakeholders.
- Among them, the legal challenges facing the development and use of generative AI needs immediate attention.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

INTRODUCTION

- Uncertainty in regulatory standards and relevant legal rights and obligations will stifle this new technology's growth and broader acceptance.
- The scope of legal protection of intellectual property rights (IPR) in generative AI training and its results raises several questions.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

INTRODUCTION

- The lack of legal harmonisation governing generative AI among different countries and legal systems will result in formidable challenges in the growth and broader adoption of the technology.
- Without specific legal provisions governing generative AI, judicial institutions in significant jurisdictions where generative AI have already started to make inroads are facing a conundrum.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

INTRODUCTION

- Early interpretative approaches of the judiciary of diverse jurisdictions in resolving disputes involving generative AI are essential sources.
- Fundamental regime and general legal standards governing copyrights and implications for engaging generative AI in producing copyrightable works.
- Emerging judicial approaches and copyright law interpretations among national Courts of common law and civil law jurisdictions.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

COPYRIGHT AND JUDICIAL RESPONSE IN USA.

- United States Code and other specific enactments on copyright that form part of the Code.
- Copyright Act of 1976 and the Digital Millennium Copyright Act of 1998.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

COPYRIGHT AND JUDICIAL RESPONSE IN USA.

- Relevant amendments to the copyright protection regime under the US Code predate the rapid expansion of AI and the more recent inception of generative AI applications.
- Under the current legislation, whether AI-produced works are copyrightable remains unsettled.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

COPYRIGHT AND JUDICIAL RESPONSE IN USA.

- Chapter 1 of the United States Code.
- Definitions of key legal terms related to copyright protection.
- Recent copyright claims dealt with by the US Courts in the case of Stephen Thaler v United States (Thaler v US) decided in August 2023.
- A key question for the Court to resolve was whether creative works generated by artificial intelligence Could be copyright-protected under US law.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

COPYRIGHT AND JUDICIAL RESPONSE IN USA.

- Various issues surround the creative process of generative AI, and intricate legal questions arise.
- What is the scope and extent of human input in the underlying process to determine whether the user of a generative AI system could be considered as an author of the resulting work?

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

COPYRIGHT AND JUDICIAL RESPONSE IN USA.

- Should the scope of copyright protection for AI-generated works be the same as the protection granted to creative human works?
- How could the work resulting from generative AI be confirmed as original works because generative AI systems are usually trained with an indeterminant amount of already existing work?

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

COPYRIGHT AND JUDICIAL RESPONSE IN USA.

- How could a balance be achieved by strictly construing the confines of copyright law while encouraging the development and use of generative AI in producing creative works?
- Legal technicality arising from applying the Administrative Procedure Act (APA) of the United States.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

COPYRIGHT AND JUDICIAL RESPONSE IN USA.

- The APA's judicial review procedure requires the Court to determine the legality of the copyright office's decision only based on the grounds of claim furnished by the copyright applicant at the time of application before the US Copyrights Office.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

COPYRIGHT AND JUDICIAL RESPONSE IN USA.

- Refusal of copyright office should be upheld based on the reasoning that the plaintiff did not play any role in using the generative AI mechanism to produce the work in question.
- The plaintiff's claim lacked human authorship, an essential trait required in any copyright application.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

COPYRIGHT AND JUDICIAL RESPONSE IN USA.

- The absence of human involvement in the creative process of works sought to be protected under the US copyright law is bound to fail.
- Despite any technological development and its use for the creative process, the fundamental requirement of human authorship is indispensable for the legal protection of copyright.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

COPYRIGHT AND JUDICIAL RESPONSE IN USA.

- Fixing a copyrightable work in a tangible medium should be carried out by the author or under his authority, underscoring the need for the author's involvement.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- Legislation enacted in 1990 and subsequently amended in 2001, 2010 and 2020
- The term work was initially defined to include works in different fields expressed in various forms.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- Works as recognised by other laws and administrative regulations (arguably expanding protection to different categories of works like AI-produced works through special legislation if the legislator so desires).
- Two essential characteristics of intellectual output and originality now read into the qualification of a work to be protected under the Chinese Copyright Law will necessarily have implications for AI-produced works.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- It is an essential mandate for the right holders to ensure that exercising the right does not infringe on the public interest.
- The state has a distinct role in supervising and managing the publication or distribution of copyrighted works.
- The general rule regarding ownership is that it belongs to the author of the copyrighted work.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- The author of a work could be a natural person who created it or a legal entity or other organisation whose intention, supervision, and responsibility were instrumental in its creation.
- When creating a work, specific rules determine who shall be entitled to the copyright.
- Rules governing works are created by combining several preexisting works, their parts, or any data that does not qualify as a work.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- Copyright in the compiled work should not be exercised prejudicial to the copyright initially vested in the preexisting work.
- The situations contemplated are reminiscent of the use of generative AI in producing copyrightable works.
- Work created by a natural person in fulfilling tasks assigned by a legal person or other organisation will qualify as work made during employment.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- A general prohibition of circumvention of protective measures and exceptional circumstances.
- Specific rules to be pertinent in the context of exploitation of protected works by generative AI.
- The state should establish a separate set of regulations explicitly governing software protection and the right to communicate information through networks.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- The increasing use of technology in China for creative works has started to trigger copyright claims and disputes related to generative AI-produced works.
- *Li v Liu 2023* provides evidence of how the Chinese courts responded to copyright claims in generative AI, the critical distinctions in the interpretative approach, and the remedies granted by the Courts of the US and China.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- The case of *Li v Liu* involved a claim of copyright for a work produced by a generative AI system used by the plaintiff and an allegation of infringement of such copyright by the defendant, leading up to an entitlement for compensation.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- Three significant issues called for determination in the dispute.
- Could the picture produced by the generative AI system be considered work for copyright law, and how could any such work be classified?

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- If a copyright persisted on the image, could its ownership be conferred upon the plaintiff?
- Whether the defendant's acts amounted to an infringement of the protected copyright concluded that the AI-generated picture can be classified as an art and expressed in a particular (electronic) form.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- Since the plaintiff, a natural person could reproduce the picture by engaging the generative AI by inputting his own prompt words and parameters, it can be classified as generated by the plaintiff using the AI.
- The Court also pointed out that generative AI producing the picture was not analogous to arranging or combining certain preset elements as programmed by a software expert.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- Distinctly, the generative AI could utilise the corresponding link between the pixels and textual information attached to the pictures in a data set and produce an original output matching the plaintiff's prompts and directions.
- This process could be equated to the functioning of a human, who has the traits of skill acquisition through learning and knowledge accumulation.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- The role of generative AI was mainly to present humans' creative ideas tangibly.
- The work in question satisfied the requirement for intellectual achievement as prescribed by copyright law.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- Did the work in question also meet the requirement of originality?
- Any intellectual output resulting from a mechanical process without an independent, personalised expression of an author will not qualify as a protected work under the copyright law.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- The generative AI system used by the plaintiff possessed the inherent capacity to produce different outputs of very personalised pictures, reflecting the diverse needs of the users that could be customised by prescribing a distinct set of specific elements as input to the system.
- Significant differences existed between the prior pictures (used as an input to the generative AI system) and the picture that was ultimately produced (as an output).

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- The process of producing the ultimate picture using different stages of review and fine-tuning on the part of the plaintiff should be considered a reflection of his personal judgement and aesthetic choice.
- Based on the finding that different persons can produce different results using the generative AI system, the picture in question should qualify as a work of originality reflecting the plaintiff's personalised expression.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- Whether the plaintiff can be considered the work's author to confer the copyright ownership.
- The AI system cannot be considered its author despite drawing the picture.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

AI-GENERATED WORKS AND COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT IN CHINA.

- The designer or the developer of the generative AI system cannot be considered an author, as he was only the creator of the tool (the AI System) and not its output, namely the work (picture) in question.
- Various behaviours of the defendant complained against constituted infringements of the plaintiff's copyright and should incur relevant liabilities prescribed under the Chinese Copyright Law.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

CONCLUDING REMARKS

- The legal regime governing copyright in the USA is not explicitly designed to cater to the needs of AI-generated copyright works.
- The judicial will seek a purposive interpretation of the existing general legal standards to meet the needs of the AI era.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

CONCLUDING REMARKS

- The Court's reluctance to recognise the scope of legal protection to the works of generative AI systems in *Thaler v. US* was due to procedural limitations rather than a lack of substantive will.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

CONCLUDING REMARKS

- An objective assessment of several holdings and related reasoning of the Court in the instant case would not permit any finding of fundamental disagreement or lack of will on the part of the Court.
- The judicial mandate in *Li v Liu* cannot be construed as a conclusive rejection of copyright protection for generative AI works in the US.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

CONCLUDING REMARKS

- In the case of China, two relevant phenomena are noticeable from the findings.
- Firstly, the legislative drive to periodically update the relevance of the copyright regime to changing economic and technological realities is visible.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

CONCLUDING REMARKS

- Secondly, the evidence of the judicial will in China to progressively interpret the general standards of copyright law in response to the generative AI technology is highly commendable.
- The Chinese court's distinct holdings and convincing reasoning in *Li v Liu* evidence of the foresight and futuristic attitude of Chinese judicial thought.

The First International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICATA-2024)

CONCLUDING REMARKS

- The discovery of diversity in judicial response to the IPR protection in generative AI among different jurisdictions should raise a necessary caveat among the international community to initiate some early intervention in developing harmonised international legal standards.
- The potential role of WIPO.